

Organic Pesticides. Part XII. Synthesis of Some Substituted Quinazol-4-ones and Related Compounds

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Several 2-methyl-3-aryl-, 2-mercapto-3-aryl-, and 2(γ -trichloro- β -hydroxy)propyl-3-aryl-quinazol-4-ones have been synthesised with a view to studying their pesticidal properties.

The wide range of biological activity of quinazolone derivatives is apparent not only from their use as antimalarials, analgesics, ataractics, and hypothermics, on which the literature is plentiful, but also in their recent application as bactericides¹ and as adjuvants with B.H.C. to kill plant weevils². It was thought of interest therefore to synthesise the compounds of the types (I) and (II), the former bearing analogy to D.D.T.-carbinol (III) which is an active acaricide³ and the latter having the toxophoric—NCS—and—SH moieties, so characteristic of many known pesticides, such as, 2-thio-3-methylbenzothiazolone⁴, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole and related compounds⁵ and thiourea, thioacetamide, thiocarbamide, and thiosemicarbazide⁶.

The 2-methyl-3-arylquinazolones have been synthesised by the method of Grimmel *et al.*⁶ These have been condensed with chloral following the method of Kulkarni⁹

1. Jain and Narang, *this Journal*, 1953, 30, 711; Sheshavratram and Subba Rao, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1959, 49, 96.
2. Chauvin *et al.*, F.P. 960, 544/1950; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1952, 46, 2232.
3. Metcalf, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1948, 41, 875.
4. Metcalf, "Organic Insecticides", p. 106.
5. Horsfall and Rich, "Contributions from Boyce Thompson Institute", 1951, 16, 329.
6. Beurer *et al.*, "Insecticides, Fungicides and Weed Killers"; Goldsworthy, *Phytopath.*, 1942, 32, 498.
8. Grimmel *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 542.
9. *This Journal*, 1942, 19, 160.

to afford 2-(γ -trichloro- β -hydroxy)propyl-3-arylquinazolones. The 2-mercapto-3-arylquinazolones have been prepared according to the method of Dave *et al.*¹⁰ by condensing anthranilic acids with arylthioureas.

EXPERIMENTAL

Halogenated Anthranilic Acids.—5-chloro-¹¹ 5-bromo-¹² and 3,5-dibromo-¹³ anthranilic acids were prepared by direct halogenation of anthranilic acid.

N-Acetylanthranilic acids were prepared by the action of acetic anhydride on anthranilic, 5-chloro-, 5-bromo-, and 3,5-dibromo-anthranilic acids in benzene¹³.

Fluoro-anilines.—3-Fluoro-, 4-fluoro¹⁴-, and 3-fluoro-4-methyl-anilines¹⁵ were prepared respectively from *m*-nitro-, *p*-nitro-, and 2-methyl-5-nitro-anilines by the Balz-Schieman reaction.

Arylthioureas.—4-Fluorophenyl- and 3-fluoro-4-methylphenyl-thioureas were prepared as described in an earlier part¹⁶.

2-Methyl-3-arylquinazol-4-ones were synthesised according to the general method of Grimmel *et al.*⁸ by refluxing under stirring a mixture of appropriate *N*-acetylanthranilic acid (0.1 *M*), amine (0.1 *M*), and PCl_3 (0.0334 *M*) in toluene (200 ml) at 130° for 2 hours. After steam distilling the toluene, the quinazolone was isolated from the residue in the usual way. The quinazolones, thus prepared, are listed in Table I.

TABLE I
2-Methyl-3-arylquinazol-4-ones.

No.	Aryl.	R.	M. P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.
1.	<i>m</i> -Fluoro-P	H	228-20°	58%	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{F}$	11.54	11.02
2.	<i>m</i> -Fluoro-P	6-Bromo	192-93°	53	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{ON}_2\text{BrF}$	8.12	8.40
3.	<i>m</i> -Fluoro-P	6-Chloro	* > 286°	60	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{ON}_2\text{ClF}$	9.20	9.70
4.	<i>p</i> -Fluoro-P	H	154-55°	57	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{F}$	11.64	11.02
5.	<i>p</i> -Fluoro-P	6-Bromo	99-101°	54	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{ON}_2\text{BrF}$	8.61	8.40
6.	3-Fluoro-4-methyl-P	H	147-48°	61	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{ON}_2\text{F}$	10.20	10.44
7.	3-Fluoro-4-methyl-P	6-Bromo	130°	49	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}_2\text{BrF}$	8.42	8.07
8.	3-Fluoro-4-methyl-P	6,8-Dibromo	97°	43	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{Br}_2\text{F}$	6.02	6.57

N.B. P-denotes phenyl

*Chars but does not melt.

¹⁰ This *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 505.

¹¹ Endicott *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1303.

¹² Wheeler *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1910, **32**, 770.

¹³ Kaufmann, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 3482.

¹⁴ Adams, "Organic Reactions", Vol. V, p. 203.

¹⁵ Schmelkes *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1631.

¹⁶ Joshi and Giri, unpublished.

2-(γ -Trichloro- β -hydroxy)propyl-3-arylquinazol-4-ones were prepared by the method of Kulkarni⁹ by refluxing a mixture of 2-methyl-3-arylquinazolone (1 *M*) and chloral (1 *M*) in an oil bath at 120-25° for 3 hours. On cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into water and allowed to stand till the pasty mass solidified. It was purified by crystallisation from dilute ethanol. The compounds, thus prepared, are listed in Table II.

TABLE II
2-(γ -Trichloro- β -hydroxy)propyl-3-aryl-quinazol-4-ones.

*No	M.P.	Yield.	**Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1.	104-105°	39%	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₃ F	6.42	6.97
2.	94-95°	43	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ BrCl ₃ F	5.23	5.82
3.	226°	47	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₄ F	6.01	6.42
4.	110-12°	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₃ F	6.25	6.97
5.	81-82°	46	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ BrCl ₄ F	5.26	5.82
6.	214-15°	45	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₃ F	6.09	6.74
7.	98-99°	41	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ BrCl ₃ F	5.14	5.66
8.	218-19°	44	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂ Cl ₃ F	4.32	4.88

*The number corresponds to the quinazolone compounds in Table I.

**Vide structure in Table I (CH₃CHOH.CCl₃ for Me).

2-Mercapto-3-arylquinazol-4-ones were prepared according to the method of Dave *et al.*¹⁰ by heating a mixture of appropriate anthranilic acid (1 *M*) and arylthiourea (1 *M*) at 180-90° for 2 hours. The pasty mass on cooling was treated with water and dissolved in dilute NaOH. The alkaline solution after filtration and acidification gave the quinazolone compound which was crystallised from rectified spirit or acetone. The compounds, thus prepared, are listed in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	Aryl.	R.	M.P.	Yield.	*Formula.	% Sulphur.	
						Found.	Reqd.
1.	<i>p</i> -Fluoro-P	H	90-91°	57%	C ₁₄ H ₉ ON ₂ FS	11.43	11.76
2.	<i>p</i> -Fluoro-P	6-Chloro	119°	51	C ₁₄ H ₈ ON ₂ ClFS	10.05	10.45
3.	<i>p</i> -Fluoro-P	6-Bromo	102°	53	C ₁₄ H ₈ ON ₂ BrFS	9.43	9.11
4.	<i>p</i> -Fluoro-P	6,8-Dibromo	116°	46	C ₁₄ H ₇ ON ₂ Br ₂ FS	7.02	7.44
5.	3-Fluoro-4-methyl-P	H	115°	40	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ON ₂ FS	11.41	11.18
6.	3-Fluoro-4-methyl-P	6-Chloro	95°	51	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ON ₂ ClFS	9.26	9.98

N. B. P denotes Phenyl.

*Vide structure in Table I (SH for Me)

The pesticidal properties of these compounds will be communicated in due course.

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